

D10.2 Report on EOSC Integration Suite and Execution Framework Requirements and Gap Analysis v.2

D10.2

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Abstract

EOSC Beyond advances the state of the art of the European Open Science Cloud by improving its Core functionalities as well as extending with new ones. Among the new ones, the Integration Suite (IS) and the Execution Framework (EF) are discussed in this document. This document is the second and final of WP10 reports on the design of IS and EF. While in the first report, D10.1, we presented the identified gaps and requirements the Integration Suite and Execution Framework were to address, in this report we present their architecture details and the implementation roadmap to address those requirements.

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Acronyms

Acronym	Meaning
DS	Deployment Service
EBTR	EOSC Beyond Technical Roadmap
EF	Execution Framework
IF	Interoperability Framework
IG	Interoperability Guideline
IS	Integration Suite

Executive Summary

This report concludes the work of EOSC Beyond Work Package 10, dedicated to the comprehensive design of two innovative services—the Integration Suite and the Execution Framework. These services aim to significantly enhance the ease of integrating new services and deploying complex applications within the EOSC Federation of Nodes, addressing previously identified gaps in interoperability and deployment flexibility.

The Integration Suite (IS) provides a structured repository of software libraries known as Adapters, facilitating seamless integration between EOSC services (both: Core and Exchange) and diverse research outputs. Built upon the EOSC Interoperability Framework Registry, the Services Catalogue, and the Marketplace, the IS promotes community-driven growth by allowing EOSC users to both contribute and utilise Adapters. Initially populated by service providers, the IS is designed to evolve organically, addressing an ever-widening array of integration scenarios shaped by community demand.

The Execution Framework (EF) complements the IS by enabling the dynamic and automated deployment of services within EOSC. Leveraging TOSCA-compliant configurations, the EF allows service providers to make their services readily deployable, and empowers researchers and end-users to effortlessly instantiate and integrate these services into tailored workflows and applications. A key strength of EF lies in its support for composability, enabling sophisticated, multi-service orchestration that significantly simplifies the creation of complex, data-driven research environments.

Building on the foundational analysis provided in the previous deliverable (D10.1), this document presents detailed component designs, interaction diagrams, and a technical roadmap guiding the upcoming implementation phase. It elaborates on the Adapter Profiles, technical specifications, and agile-driven planning instruments, laying clear groundwork for practical development.

With the completion of this deliverable, Work Package 10 hands over the designed specifications and plans to Work Packages 11 and 13, responsible respectively for the development and implementation of the Integration Suite and the Execution Framework. Future deliverables from these work packages will document the progress, evaluate implementations, and showcase demonstration scenarios leveraging these innovative services.

1. Introduction

In this second report on the design process for the Integration Suite (IS) and Execution Framework (EF), we document the progress made in the past months in the designing and preparation for implementation to be carried out by Work Packages 11 (IS) and 13 (EF).

These new services – IS and EF – are part of our effort to streamline the new services integration and applications deployment in the EOSC Beyond Network of Nodes.

In the previous deliverable, D10.1¹, we presented the gaps in the current EOSC services offering and drew service requirements as the foundation for designing our solutions. Since then, we have been focused on detailing the components and steps towards implementation:

- **Designing IS and EF components:** beyond the services involved as previously presented, the actual components and their interactions;
- **Defining the technical roadmap:** using agile methodologies' instruments – requirements, user stories, epics and tasks – to define elements of implementation;
- **Adapters Profile:** the metadata set of attributes to describe an Adapter as an EOSC resource.

1.1. Scope and purpose of the document

This document is the second and last report of Work Package 10, in charge of the design of IS and EF. For the design, we prepared:

1. Diagrams depicting flow of actions and interactions between components;
2. Technical Roadmap structuring development tickets.

Those elements are being used to describe the design of both new services – IS and EF – as well as the Adapters and the Composability-based Applications EOSC Beyond is to deliver as demonstration cases of IS and EF, respectively.

As the second report, this document is more direct to the elements being discussed, skipping most of the fundamental discussions that composed the previous report, D10.1. The reason is to avoid an unnecessary elongated document so we can keep the focus on the actual material being delivered: the design.

The document contains many inline references of the type “**EBTR-*number***”, those are references to the project's technical roadmap, EOSC Beyond's Jira project for all tickets related to the implementation and improvement of the services. Such content is not meant for public access, yet we chose to put the links (inline) in this document for two reasons: (1) to display the granularity of our specifications for the external reader, (2) to serve as a reference for the project participants from other Work Packages.

¹ <https://zenodo.org/records/14204589>

1.2. Structure of the document

- **Section 2:** brief introduction to the Integration Suite
 - Design elements of IS and its components;
 - List of Adapters and design status.
- **Section 3:** brief introduction to the Execution Framework
 - Design elements of EF and its components;
 - Design status of the Composability-based applications.
- **Section 4:** final remarks and conclusion.

2. Integration Suite

IS is a service built upon three existing EOSC components, offering software libraries—known as Adapters—to streamline integration with EOSC services and other research outputs. In essence, the IS functions as an open digital repository of software packages associated with specific EOSC resources, allowing any EOSC user to contribute or utilise these offerings.

This suite is underpinned by three established EOSC services (the Interoperability Framework (IF) Registry, the Services Catalogue, and the Marketplace, which facilitates the onboarding and ordering of resources) intertwined with the Discovery Hub, which provides discoverability. For simplicity, we will use the term "Marketplace" throughout this deliverable; however, it should be understood as referring to two interconnected services: Marketplace and Discovery Hub. Each has been enhanced to support Adapters in distinct ways:

- IF Registry hosts Adapter definitions;
- Services Catalogue enables providers to create and manage Adapter records;
- Marketplace promotes Adapters, making them discoverable to users.

Adapters are tightly coupled with IF Guidelines. While the Guidelines define the standards and interfaces needed for interoperability, Adapters leverage these definitions to extend a service's interface and functionality.

Initially, service owners will supply the first set of Adapters to populate the Integration Suite. Over time, as the EOSC community contributes more Adapters, the IS will expand to accommodate an increasing number of use cases driven by collective needs and demand.

The specific roles of the IF Registry, Services Catalogue, and Marketplace in IS are outlined in the following section.

2.1. Service Design

As previously mentioned, IS is responsible for providing Adapters to the EOSC community and it does so through other service components. This includes other EOSC core services as well as external services responsible for storing the actual code, documentation and other artifacts relevant to the proper functioning of the Adapter.

[Figure 2-1](#) presents the component services diagram for the IS, and how they participate in the workflows of *publishing* and *consuming* Adapters.

Figure 2-1. Integration Suite architecture and workflow diagram.

The metadata describing Adapters is defined by the *Adapters Profile*. The metadata set is stored and managed internally by the Integration Suite, while the software package, source code, documentation is stored outside the IS, at the Adapter provider's discretion.

Specifically, the metadata set is stored by the IF Registry once it has been created/edited by the Adapter's provider through the Providers Dashboard. Users – *i.e.*, potential consumers – search and access Adapters (metadata) through Marketplace (Discovery Hub).

[Table 2-1](#) presents the metadata attributes of the Adapters' Profile. At the top of the table, under *software attributes*, we want to highlight the attributes that locate the software content the user will eventually install, read, use. Those are independent URLs since it is usually the case that developers will use different (free or paid) platforms for hosting each of the elements.

Table 2-1. Metadata attributes describing Adapters (Profile).

Attribute	Description	Cardinality	Datatype
Software attributes			
repository	Code repository webpage (eg, Github repository)	1	URL
package	Link to latest package release page (eg, PyPI project, Docker image, Github releases page)	1-N	URL
documentation	Documentation webpage (eg, read-the-docs page)	1	URL
Descriptive attributes			
id	(unique) Identifier	1	string
name	(unique) name	1	string
description	long description	1	string
guideline	EOSC Guideline	1	string (CV)
service	EOSC Service	0-N	string (CV)
tagline	short description (catch-phrase)	0-1	string
logo	logo	0-1	image
programmingLanguage	Programming language	1-N	string (CV)
license	Software/Code license (eg, MIT, Apache, GPL)	1	string (CV)
version	Software version	1	string
changeLog	Changes in the latest version	1	string

Attribute	Description	Cardinality	Datatype
lastUpdate	Latest update date	1	date
Provider attributes			
maintainers	Maintainer names (people and/or org)	1-N	object
email	Maintainer or organisation contact email	1-N	email
organisation	Name of the organisation (institute, company, university, research group, department, etc)	0-1	string
organisationURL	Organisation website	0-1	URL
funding	Funding organisation, program, grant supporting the Adapter's development or maintenance	0-N	string

Figure 2-2 provides a closer view of the relationship between the *content* of an Adapter – i.e., the software library and its artefacts – and the *metadata* of an Adapter – i.e., its Profile.

Figure 2-2. Detailed view of Adapters' content and IS publication.

2.1.1. Technical Roadmap

In the previous report, D10.1, we presented a set of software requirements defined on the basis of user demands elicited by EOSC Beyond Pilots (D15.1²), as well as known gaps defined in the project's proposal.

Such requirements were used as the starting point in defining the technical roadmap to be carried on by WP11 in the implementation of IS. On top of the service requirements, user stories and epics were created in the project's internal Jira platform, defining the necessary steps to accomplish the implementation of the service.

[Table 2-2](#) presents user stories instrumental in delineating user journeys across the services and from there, defining epics and tasks. [Figure 2-3](#) presents the same user stories in a diagram for a more comprehensive view.

Table 2-2. User stories and journeys relating to EOSC service components.

#	Title	Story	Journey	Component
1	Publish an Adapter	A service provider wants to share an Adapter, e.g. a Python wrapper for a service API they have developed.	-> User: log in to the portal and choose "create adapter"	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Providers Dashboard
			-> System: render webpage with Adapter's Profile form to be filled	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Providers Dashboard
			-> User: fill the mandatory/optional fields in the form	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Providers Dashboard
			-> System: validate values and commit values to Adapter's data store	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Providers Dashboard IF Registry
			-> System: release Adapter to the public and display the Adapter's page to the	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> IF Registry Marketplace

² <https://zenodo.org/records/13152335>

#	Title	Story	Journey	Component
			user	
2	Onboard an Adapter	A service provider implemented a Python wrapper for a service (REST API) they use and wants to share it.	-> System: provide documentation/guideline on how to onboard an Adapter	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • IF Registry • Providers Dashboard • Marketplace
3	Find Adapter	A service provider would like to search for a Python wrapper for a service API they use.	-> User: go to Marketplace, search using "Adapter" related filters (Adapters search view, Guidelines search, or Services search)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Marketplace
			-> System: query the Registry and return list of Adapters found	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Marketplace • IF Registry
			-> User: select Adapter of interest for details	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Marketplace
			-> System: renders Adapter page	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Marketplace
			-> User: follow Adapter links for documentation and package for download and use instructions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>External systems used by Adapter's provider</i>
4	Report a safety issue	A service provider found a critical	-> User: go to Adapter's webpage and report a	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Marketplace

#	Title	Story	Journey	Component
		vulnerability in the Adapter and wants to communicate with the "EOSC Node" about it so the affected systems can react accordingly.	"critical" issue	

Figure 2-3. User stories and journeys diagram.

To achieve this, the IS will implement a dedicated user interface within the Providers Dashboard for creating and editing Adapters (EBTR-115), supported by an Adapter database (EBTR-112). Furthermore, it will define a standardised Adapter Profile (metadata schema) to ensure consistency (EBTR-108), and include features for Adapter ownership transfer among service providers (EBTR-116).

To streamline the onboarding process, detailed documentation will be provided (EBTR-111), enforcing a clear guideline-adapter association model where each Adapter must relate explicitly to exactly one guideline (EBTR-109), while optionally linking to multiple services (EBTR-110). An approval workflow will also be defined and integrated into the Providers Dashboard to manage Adapter publications effectively (EBTR-113).

To facilitate Adapter discovery, the Marketplace component will be enhanced to include dedicated search and filtering functionalities ([EBTR-178](#), [EBTR-179](#)). Users can then discover Adapters easily, exploring comprehensive Adapter details ([EBTR-240](#)). An API for querying Adapters will also be integrated into the IF Registry to support the Marketplace searches ([EBTR-114](#)).

To uphold robust governance and security practices, mechanisms will be introduced for reporting and managing safety issues identified in Adapters. Users will have a dedicated "Report Critical Issue" feature available through the Marketplace, promptly notifying service providers and triggering predefined governance policies to manage Adapter security issues effectively ([EBTR-144](#)).

Providers Dashboard and Service Registry

The Providers Dashboard is currently providing a UI for Providers to:

- Onboard and manage their own Interoperability Guidelines in the IF Registry;
- Link Guidelines onboarded (by them or other Providers) in the IF Registry to their own Services.

[Figure 2-4](#) emphasises the components designed for implementation.

Figure 2-4. Providers Dashboard, Service Registry and Interoperability Registry architecture diagram.

This UI serves as the frontend for the Service Registry and Interoperability Guideline backend components, which in turn are responsible for storage of onboarded services and Guidelines respectively.

With the addition of the Adapters Onboarding capability, the Providers Dashboard will enhance the UI interface so as for Providers to onboard and link Adapters to Interoperability Guidelines ([EBTR-115](#), [EBTR-287](#)).

Moreover, the Providers Portal will evolve to provide a UI for:

- Creating Configuration Templates for Interoperability Guidelines. These templates will serve as definitions for Guideline parameters that can be instantiated for Services that adhere to these Guidelines;
- Add the ability for Providers to create and edit Configuration Template instances through the UI;
- Service Registry will also evolve to support Configuration Template instances linking and storage to onboarded Services through API ([EBTR-114](#)).

IF Registry

The IF Registry is currently providing an API for onboarding and managing Interoperability Guidelines, which are metadata collections and URLs/links to human readable instructions on how services can become compliant to them. It will evolve to:

- Support onboarding and linking Adapters to Guidelines through APIs;
- Support Configuration templates definition and linking to Guidelines; this will allow guidelines to evolve from being human readable instructions to become machine readable specifications.

Marketplace

The Marketplace is designed to simplify the discovery, ordering, and usage of research resources, ensuring that scientists can efficiently set up their research environments and focus on innovation. It serves as a central hub for discovering publications, datasets, services, Interoperability Guidelines, and much more.

Currently, the Marketplace enables the onboarding of the following entities (including their relationships) via the Providers Dashboard:

- Providers;
- Services;
- Data Sources;
- Training materials;
- Interoperability Guidelines.

Moving forward, the Marketplace will also support the onboarding of IS Adapters ([EBTR-180](#), [EBTR-240](#)). These Adapters will be linked to both guidelines and services, ensuring seamless interoperability while clearly presenting their relationships within the Adapters' view ([EBTR-179](#)). Additionally, users will be able to explore these relationships in the service and guideline views, with the option to filter and refine their search based on these connections

([EBTR-178](#), [EBTR-239](#)). [Figure 2-5](#) depicts the new API endpoints between the Service Catalogue and the Marketplace

Figure 2-5. Marketplace and Service Catalogue integration interface.

The onboarding of deployable services in the Marketplace is described in the section dedicated to EF and the Marketplace. Based on the Adapters Profile ([Table 2-1](#)), the initial design for the Adapter Detail Page view is presented in [Figure 2-6](#).

Figure 2-6. Initial design for Marketplace Adapter Detail Page based on the Adapter Profile.

2.2. Adapters for EOSC Services

Adapters are here to facilitate the integration of systems. In the networking model EOSC Beyond is developing, nodes are free to deploy only the services that suit their needs. This means that a node does not need to deploy all the core services, it can rather use another node's services to enhance its own services with other capabilities. In such a scenario, there are two modes of integration between services of two different nodes: (i) when two services are able to exchange information between them directly, and (ii) when two services need a middleware component to achieve interoperability. The latter is the case for Adapters.

Adapters can be used to integrate two services with the same function that may for some reason be unable to exchange information directly. They can also be used to integrate two services from different domains to provide a better user experience, for example.

2.2.1. Helpdesk

The helpdesk service is based on Zammad, an open-source, self-hosted, feature-rich ticketing system platform.

Table 2-3: Helpdesk adapter.

PROXY STANDALONE ADAPTER	
Top-level Diagram of the helpdesk adapter	<p>The diagram shows a central 'Adapter' represented by three interlocking gears. To the left is a box labeled 'Node Helpdesk' and to the right is a box labeled 'EOSC Helpdesk'. Double-headed arrows labeled 'API' connect the Node Helpdesk to the Adapter, and the Adapter to the EOSC Helpdesk, indicating bidirectional communication.</p>
Description	A proxy that enables bidirectional synchronisation between two helpdesk platforms through a REST API, requiring minimal development effort and allowing real-time exchange of tickets, user data, and status updates.
Requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improve integration with EOSC Core components (EBTR-87)
Epics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development of Helpdesk Adapter and improve helpdesk integration capacities (EBTR-251)
Guideline	EOSC Helpdesk: Architecture and Interoperability Guidelines ³

2.2.2. PID

The EOSC PID Service provides a service to maintain Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) based on B2HANDLE, which provides a distributed service for storing, managing and accessing persistent identifiers and their essential metadata (PID records).

Table 2-4: PID adapter.

PID ADAPTER	
Description	<p>The Adapter for the PID service enables seamless communication between the PID service and EOSC Core components, such as catalogues, by using standardised protocols and APIs.</p> <p>Adapter will provide functionality for catalogues:</p>

³ <https://zenodo.org/records/8009651>

PID ADAPTER	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> to mint, list, maintain, delete persistent identifiers using the EOSC PID services (CRUD PIDs), and also resolving the PID records. to authenticate themselves to the EOSC PID services.
Requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Requirements for Adapter Integration with EOSC PID Services (EBTR-333)
Epics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> PID Adapter (EBTR-262)
Guideline	N/A


```

graph TD
    subgraph PID_Service [PID Service]
        API[PID - API  
[Component: API]  
PID Service]
        DS[(PID DataStore  
[Container: Relational Database]  
Contains PIDs and Prefixes)]
        API -- "Fetch PID data" --> DS
    end
    ES[External system name  
[Software System]  
Description of external software system.] -- "Mint Pids" --> AD[PID Adaptor  
[Software System]  
PID Adaptor]
    AD -- "Mint Pids" --> API
    
```

2.2.3. IF Registry

The EOSC IF Registry adds a thin semantic layer on top of the EOSC resource catalogue that allows viewing (and discovery, browsing, etc.) EOSC resources in the EOSC Catalogue in terms of their compliance with IF Guidelines.

Table 2-5: IF Registry adapters.

IF REGISTRY ADAPTERS	
Guideline	EOSC Service Catalogue: Architecture and Interoperability Guidelines ⁴
INTEROPERABILITY GUIDELINE DISCOVERY ADAPTER	
Description	Adapter will provide functionality for: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • searching, browsing, and navigating the IF Guidelines which are onboarded to a Interoperability Registry instance • ability to broker/route metadata information to service providers and any other EOSC Core component that uses such data
Requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adapters for Interoperability Framework Registry (EBTR-329)
Epics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interoperability Framework Registry Core Adapter (EBTR-284)

⁴ <https://zenodo.org/records/8333871>

INTEROPERABILITY GUIDELINE MANAGEMENT ADAPTER	
Description	<p>Adapter will provide functionality for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● providers, to register to the EOSC to become eligible for the onboarding of IF Guidelines ● providers, to onboard their Guidelines into the EOSC Interoperability Registry ● providers, to view the list of Guidelines registered in the EOSC portal and perform a variety of actions such as activate, deactivate, update newer versions, and view statistics of Guidelines referenced by services.
Requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Adapters for Interoperability Framework Registry (EBTR-329)
Epics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Interoperability Framework Registry Core Adapter (EBTR-284)

2.2.4. Service Catalogue

Service Catalogue offers the underlying storage functionality and the interoperability tools for the programmatic access, registration, manage (CRUD) of providers, services, and catalogues. It offers

- the necessary API functionality for the interoperability of service catalogues from individual providers or aggregators (e.g., thematic, or regional catalogues) with the EOSC portal
- the front-end functionality for the registration of EOSC Providers, organisations entitled to publish their resources via the EOSC Catalogue, and offers them capabilities to onboard and manage EOSC resources. This is done through the Providers Dashboard, where representatives from provider organisations have a detailed view on their offerings in the EOSC portal as well as various usage statistics on their resources. Finally, it offers to members of the onboarding team of the EOSC portal the functionality to manage the EOSC portal catalogue entries, i.e., manage the onboarding process of providers that apply to list their resources in the portal, audit on the onboarded resources, etc.

Currently, the following Adapters are planned:

Table 2-6: Service Catalogue adapters.

⁵ <https://zenodo.org/records/8333871>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Searching, browsing, and navigating the services and Providers which are onboarded to a Service Catalogue instance • Ability to broker/route metadata information to service providers and any other EOSC Core component that uses such data
Requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adapters for Service Catalogue (EBTR-288)
Epics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Service Catalogue Core Adapters implementation (EBTR-279)
PROVIDER AND SERVICE MANAGEMENT ADAPTER	
Description	<p>Adapter will provide functionality for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Providers, to register to the EOSC to become eligible for the onboarding of resources • Providers, to onboard their services into the EOSC Service Catalogue • Providers, to view the list of services registered in the EOSC portal and perform a variety of actions such as activate, deactivate, view usage statistics
Requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adapters for Service Catalogue (EBTR-288)
Epics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Service Catalogue Core Adapters implementation (EBTR-279)
ADMINISTRATION AND AUDIT ADAPTER	
Description	<p>Adapter will provide functionality for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Managing the onboarding process (approve, reject an application), • Managing the catalogue of providers and services and audit the validity of the catalogue entries • Interacting with providers through EOSC established channels (Helpdesk) • Adding catalogues from regional or thematic Nodes
Requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adapters for Service Catalogue (EBTR-288)

Epics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Service Catalogue Core Adapters implementation (EBTR-279)
STATISTICS AND INSIGHTS ADAPTER	
Description	<p>Adapter will provide functionality for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Catalogue statistics Recommendations and insights based on the catalogue feedback and content
Requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Adapters for Service Catalogue (EBTR-288)
Epics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Service Catalogue Core Adapters implementation (EBTR-279)

2.2.5. Monitoring

Monitoring is the key service needed to gain insights into an infrastructure. It needs to be continuous and on-demand to quickly detect, correlate, and analyse data for a fast reaction to anomalous behaviour before the latter affects end-users and ultimately the productivity of the organisation. Management teams can monitor the availability and reliability of the services from a high level view down to individual system metrics and the conformance of multiple SLAs.

Table 2-7: Monitoring adapter.

MONITORING ADAPTER	
Description	<p>The service is currently accessible only via an API, requiring each client to develop custom integrations to interact with it. This can be both time-consuming and complex, as developers must build tailored solutions for various use cases. To simplify this process, a Python-based Adapter will be introduced. This Adapter will act as a wrapper around the existing API, making it easier to connect to the Argo Monitoring Service by managing the underlying API calls. With this Adapter, developers can more easily integrate and automate the collection and exchange of metrics.</p> <p>Key goals of the Adapter include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Streamlined Integrations: It will focus on frequently used API calls, such as publishing metrics, to simplify the integration process.

MONITORING ADAPTER	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Simplified Interface: Complex API calls will be abstracted into easy-to-use Python functions, with common parameters automatically handled. ● Error Handling: It will centralise error management, converting raw API errors into meaningful Python exceptions and incorporating retry logic to enhance reliability.
Requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Need for a Simplified Integration Solution for the Monitoring Service (EBTR-331)
Epics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Monitoring Adapter (EBTR-259)
Guideline	EOSC Monitoring: Architecture and Interoperability Guidelines ⁶

⁶ <https://zenodo.org/records/8333926>

2.2.6. Messaging

The ARGO Messaging Service (AMS) is a robust, real-time messaging platform designed to facilitate seamless communication between independent applications by enabling the exchange of messages. It acts as a middleware service, allowing different components, services, or applications to send and receive messages efficiently, even if they are developed independently or reside on different systems. This makes AMS ideal for microservices architectures, distributed systems, and other scenarios where multiple applications need to communicate reliably and at scale.

Table 2-8: Messaging adapter.

MESSAGING ADAPTER	
Description	<p>Currently, AMS offers a Python library that provides the core functionalities of the service such as message publishing, subscribing, and queue management. However, to meet the evolving needs of various services within the project, there is a requirement to enhance this library by adding new features and extending existing ones. The project aims to build on the existing capabilities of the AMS library by introducing new features such as advanced message filtering, support for different message formats, and improved error handling.</p> <p>The Adapter's planned enhancements are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Extended Coverage: Within the scope of this project, we will expand the coverage of existing functionalities to improve the overall user experience. ● Support for New Functionalities: We will add support for new features to be developed, enhancing the Adapter's capabilities and adaptability to various client requirements. <p>Some of the extra capabilities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Batch Processing: If the other services require, you could extend the AMS library to support batch message processing. ● Custom Message Formats: add support for custom message formats based on the schema support.
Requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Need for Batch Processing and Custom Message Format Support (EBTR-332)

2.2.7. Accounting for Services

The Accounting Service is a robust platform designed to streamline metrics collection, aggregation, and exchange across diverse infrastructures, providers, and projects.

Currently, the service is accessible only through an API, which implies that each client must develop its own integration to interact with. This approach can be time-consuming and complex, as developers need to build custom solutions for every use case. To address this challenge, the service will be enhanced with the introduction of a Python-based Adapter. This Adapter will serve as a wrapper around the existing API, simplifying the process of connecting to the Accounting Service. By handling the underlying API calls, the Adapter will make it easier for developers to integrate and automate the collection and exchange of metrics.

Table 2-9: Accounting for Service adapter.

ACCOUNTING FOR SERVICES ADAPTER	
Description	<p>The initial version of the Adapter will focus on the most commonly used functionalities, including publishing and retrieving accounting metrics. This will streamline the process of building Accounting agents for various services, reducing development time and effort.</p> <p>The Adapter's aims will be:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Focus on the most frequently used API calls such as metrics publishing aiming to simplify the creation of clients. • Simplified Interface: It will abstract complex API calls into easy-to-use Python functions, automatically handling common parameters to simplify usage. • Error Handling: It will centralise error handling by converting raw API errors into meaningful Python exceptions and it will include retry logic to improve reliability.
Requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Simplify interface of the Accounting Service (EBTR-330)
Epics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Accounting for Services Adapter (EBTR-261)
Guideline	EOSC Accounting for Services interoperability Guideline ⁷

⁷ <https://zenodo.org/records/10843159>

2.2.8. Research Product Catalogue

Data Sources can onboard research products (publications, data, and software) into the Research Product Catalogue by implementing the EOSC IF Guidelines for Data Sources. As part of the implementation, Data Sources need to export metadata of research products via the OAI-PMH protocol.

In EOSC Beyond we have developed an Adapter that facilitates the process of onboarding for data sources managing metadata of research products using PostgreSQL Databases.

Table 2-10: Research Product Catalogue adapter.

OAI-PMH end-point for SQL Postgres Databases	
Description	This Adapter consists of a Spring Boot application designed to facilitate the export of metadata records in compliance with the Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting (OAI-PMH). The application operates as an OAI-PMH endpoint that efficiently collects and exports metadata directly from a PostgreSQL database. By adhering to OAI-PMH standards, this application enhances the accessibility and interoperability of metadata across diverse digital libraries and repositories ⁸ .

⁸ <https://zenodo.org/records/13938870>

OAI-PMH end-point for SQL Postgres Databases	
Requirements	N/A
Epics	N/A
Guideline	EOSC-IF Interoperability Guidelines for Data Sources to onboard Research Products ⁹

The diagram shows a workflow starting from a 'Data Source' (represented by a blue cylinder) which feeds into an 'OAI-PMH Adapter' (a red rounded rectangle). An arrow labeled 'Harvesting' points from the adapter to the 'OpenAIRE Graph' (a red logo with a plus sign). Another arrow points from the graph to 'EOSC KG' (a network graph icon). A separate path shows an 'Onboarding' arrow pointing up to a box containing 'Onboarding of Resources' and the 'OpenAIRE PROVIDE' logo.

2.2.9. Research Products Accounting

Research Product Accounting is provided via the OpenAIRE Usage Counts Service, which in turn provides EOS IF guidelines¹⁰ for data source managers to participate in the service, using methods and standards to collect and process usage data to generate comparable, standards-based usage statistics. These guidelines align with Release 4 of the COUNTER Code of Practice for e-Resources¹¹.

⁹ <https://zenodo.org/records/8362321>

¹⁰ <https://openaire.github.io/usage-statistics-guidelines>

¹¹ <https://www.projectcounter.org/wp-content/uploads/2016/02/APPD.pdf>

As part of the offer, OpenAIRE provides Adapters, i.e. tracking code for repository platforms, which can be easily installed by repository managers to federate to the EOSC Accounting for Research Products and share their statistics. By adhering to the COUNTER protocol, repositories will:

- **Tracking Usage Events:** They track usage events from the repository, such as item downloads and metadata views.
- **Adhering to Standards:** These plugins apply COUNTER rules on usage data and store them in a statistics database, ensuring compliance with the COUNTER Code of Practice Release 4 for processing usage events and generating usage statistics reports.
- **Providing Standardised Metrics:** By utilising open standards and protocols, these plugins help gather usage data and consolidate usage statistics reports from distributed data providers.

Table 2-11: Research Products Accounting adapters.

¹² <https://zenodo.org/records/8362353>

¹³ <https://github.com/openaire/OpenAIRE-Piwik-DSpace>

Epics	N/A
COUNTER Adapter for generic platforms	
Description	The Adapter connects generic repository platforms with the EOSC Accounting for Research Products (OpenAIRE UsageCounts) ¹⁴
Requirements	N/A
Epics	N/A
COUNTER Adapter for ePrints platform	
Description	The Adapter connects ePrints platforms with the EOSC Accounting for Research Products (OpenAIRE UsageCounts) ¹⁵
Requirements	N/A
Epics	N/A

2.2.10. Data Transfer

The Data Transfer¹⁶ (DT) service allows users to transfer datasets to different storage facilities through an easy-to-use GUI as well as a REST API. DT provides an API that can also be used directly by other EOSC services (e.g. the Deployment Service) and researchers.

Table 2-12: Data Transfer adapter.

Data Transfer Python client	
Description	A Python client for Data Transfer's REST API.

¹⁴ <https://github.com/openaire/Generic-Matomo-Tracker>

¹⁵ <https://github.com/openaire/EPrints-OAPiwik>

¹⁶ <https://github.com/egi-federation/eosc-data-transfer>

Data Transfer Python client	
Requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide language-specific API client libraries (EBTR-266)
Epics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop an API Python client for Data Transfer (EBTR-267) • Release Data Transfer API client through GitHub (EBTR-268)
Guideline	EOSC Data Transfer: Architecture and Interoperability Guideline ¹⁷

Data Transfer Adapter

EOSC Data Transfer API

Data Transfer Engine (e.g. EGI Data Transfer)

EOSC Users

Dataset Repository

Storage collocated with computing

Legend

- Commands (dashed line)
- Data (solid line)

Parse dataset repositories
Create and query transfer jobs
Manipulate storage elements

Request and Monitor data transfer

Parse files in dataset

Data from dataset

Data to storage

Manage storage elements

2.2.11. Deployment Service

The Deployment Service (DS), based on the Infrastructure Manager (IM)¹⁸, aims to provide a mechanism to automate the integration and composability of data sources, software tools and computing infrastructures.

¹⁷ <https://zenodo.org/records/7925515>

¹⁸ <https://im.egi.eu>

Table 2-13: Deployment Service adapters.

APRICOTLab (DS Jupyter Notebook Adapter)	
Description	This Adapter is responsible for providing extensions in Jupyter that allow users to employ the functionality of the DS from a Jupyter Notebook.
Requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The DS should be accessible from multiple interfaces (EBTR-8)
Epics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The DS should be accessible from multiple interfaces (EBTR-129)
Guideline	Guideline for TOSCA deployable services (In progress)
<p>The diagram shows a user interacting with a JupyterHub Instance. Inside the instance, the APRICOTLab adapter is active. This adapter provides access to Virtual Machines (VMs) within a Cloud Provider. Additionally, a Deployment Service is shown, which is responsible for deploying infrastructure into the Cloud Provider.</p>	

Metadata gathering of TOSCA templates	
Description	This Adapter will facilitate the access of TOSCA template metadata offered by the DS through its OAI-PMH interface.
Requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> DS OAI-PMH protocol support (EBTR-12)

Metadata gathering of TOSCA templates	
Epics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Support DS OAI-PMH protocol (EBTR-133)
Guideline	Guideline for TOSCA deployable services (In progress)
<pre> graph TD User((User)) -- Search TOSCA templates --> Harvester[OAI-PMH Harvester] Harvester -- Harvest TOSCA templates --> Adapter[OAI-PMH Adapter] subgraph DS [Deployment Service] Adapter end Adapter --> Repo[(TOSCA templates repo)] </pre>	

2.2.12. Data access across hosting environment

Table 2-14: Data access adapters.

Data access across hosting environment	
Description	The JupyterLab Adapter securely integrates external storage via link sharing and access tokens, enabling flexible data mounts. It includes a JupyterLab extension, REST API, JupyterHub Spawner, and documentation.
Requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Use external storage location within Jupyter environments (EBTR-348)
Epics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Jupyter Data Access - Implementation (EBTR-347) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> JupyterLab Data Mount Extension (EBTR-340) Data Mount REST API (EBTR-341) JupyterHub Spawner (EBTR-345)

Data access across hosting environment	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Document Adapter Setup and Usage (EBTR-346)
Guideline	N/A
<p style="text-align: center;">Simplified systems diagram (eg, C4 model level 2)</p>	

2.2.13. Python libraries for EOSC core and exchange services

Jupyter Command-line client	
Description	<p>This Adapter will provide users with an ability to remotely control their user instances on hosted JupyterHub services via a CLI client. This includes control of the state of their user instances and also allows them to directly leverage potential tools inside Jupyter notebooks like papermill¹⁹, a tool allowing batch processing, without having to start up a browser. This could be very useful in automated workflows.</p>

¹⁹ <https://papermill.readthedocs.io/en/latest/index.html>

Jupyter Command-line client	
Requirements	N/A
Epics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improved integration with other EOSC Core components (EBTR-151)
Guideline	N/A

```

graph TD
    Client[Client fedcloud cli] -- "fedcloud jupyterhub..." --> JupyterHub[JupyterHub]
    JupyterHub -- "start, stop server...." --> Server[Single user server]
    Client -- "upload, alter files...." --> Server
    Client -- "exec command.." --> Extension[Extension]
    Server --> Extension
    Extension -- "os.run(...)" --> Notebooks[User notebooks - *.ipynb...]
    Extension -- "papermill" --> Notebooks
    
```

3. Execution Framework

The EOSC Execution Framework (EF) is designed to facilitate the dynamic deployment and composability of services within the EOSC ecosystem. Unlike traditional service catalogues that merely list available resources, the EF enables service providers to offer deployable instances of their onboarded services, while end users can configure, deploy and integrate these instances into custom workflows and applications.

A fundamental aspect of the EF is its support for TOSCA-compliant execution configurations, allowing services to be instantiated with predefined or user-defined parameters. This

capability ensures greater flexibility and interoperability, enabling researchers and service providers to tailor deployments to specific computational and analytical needs. Through the EOSC Marketplace, users can select a “deployable service” and launch service instances, defining their execution environment while ensuring compatibility with EOSC-wide standards and guidelines.

Beyond individual deployments, the EF fosters composability, allowing multiple services to be combined into higher-order solutions. This capability is particularly valuable for researchers and data-driven applications that rely on seamless integration between different computational, storage and analytical resources. By enabling this level of service orchestration, the EF reduces the complexity associated with manual configuration and deployment, streamlining the user experience.

The framework is designed to serve three primary user groups:

- **Service providers:** They can configure and make their services deployable by defining access parameters and execution templates based on TOSCA specifications. This ensures that services are offered in a structured and standardised manner;
- **Researchers and end users:** They can deploy services dynamically, adjusting configurations as needed and integrating multiple services into their workflows. This allows them to create customised data-driven applications without requiring in-depth infrastructure management expertise;
- **Developers, system administrators and software engineers:** They ensure the integration and interoperability of the services within the broader EOSC ecosystem, maintaining compliance with the EOSC Interoperability Framework and its associated guidelines.

By supporting automated deployment, structured service orchestration and composability, the EOSC Execution Framework enhances the accessibility and usability of EOSC resources. This enables a more efficient research environment where users can move from service discovery to execution in a streamlined and interoperable manner.

3.1. Technical roadmap

As part of Deliverable D10.1, we initiated a gap analysis for the services described. The diagram below ([Figure 3-1](#)) illustrates a high-level overview of the service workflow and interactions within EF. It highlights the interactions between key components: the IF Registry and Deployment Service, which are central to the Execution Framework, alongside the Marketplace and Resource Catalogue.

- **Resource Catalogue:** Manages a collection of interoperable EOSC resources, ensuring effective resource organisation and utilisation. The EOSC Resource Catalogue has been extended to handle a new type of entity, namely Deployable Services, intended as TOSCA recipes (software and installations scripts) that can be automatically deployed to deliver an operational service;

- **IF Registry:** Oversees the management of Integration Guidelines and corresponding configurations, ensuring that services can expose information about the actual API endpoints as described by the EOSC guidelines they are compliant with;
- **Deployment Service:** Functions as the core component responsible for orchestrating the deployment of Deployable Service resources onboarded in the EOSC Resource Catalogue and exposed via the Marketplace;
- **Marketplace:** Acts as the user interface for discovering and selecting Services and Deployable services, facilitates the configuration of user-defined parameters to the Deployment Service.

Figure 3-1. Execution Framework architecture diagram.

Given such an architecture, we envisage the following workflow can be supported:

1. A user onboards (registers) a Deployable Service to the Service Catalogue (in turn to the EOSC Resource Catalogue);
2. The Marketplace makes the Deployable Service discoverable and automatically creates an offer for it by fetching input values from the provided TOSCA recipe;
3. An end user finds the Deployable Services in the Marketplace and places an order for the underlying offer, specifying dynamic parameters;
4. The Marketplace sends a request for deployment to the Deployment Service which will return the end point of the service environment.

As part of the roadmap, the connection between the Deployment Service and a cloud provider, and the match-making of a TOSCA recipe and a cloud package, will be investigated. Aspects such as decoupling of TOSCA from multiple cloud providers, as well as match-making cloud provider offers and TOSCA recipes need to be addressed. On the other hand, for the purpose of experimentation, we will consider starting from a static interoperation with one cloud provider (e.g. EGI) and build on stricter assumptions regarding the match-making.

The roadmap is structured into key functional domains, each with a set of requirements linked to user stories and development epics. We have four main use-case scenarios, described more in detail in [Table 3-1](#).

Service Deployment and Composability

A major goal of the EF is to ensure that services can be onboarded as deployable entities, allowing researchers and end users to instantiate services dynamically. To achieve this, the EOSC Deployment Service and Service Catalogue must support a structured onboarding process. Deployable Service providers must be able to register their resources for other users to both find them via the Marketplace and reuse them to deploy an actual service ([EBTR-270](#)).

Additionally, to enhance research workflows, users should be able to compose multiple deployed services into higher-order applications. This requires the EOSC Interoperability Framework to facilitate service discovery and metadata-driven composability. The EF will support linking Adapters to services, making it easier to implement workflows combining services and computational resources ([EBTR-270](#)).

Data Transfer and Automation

A key requirement for researchers working with large datasets is efficient, secure and automated data transfer. The EOSC Data Transfer Service will facilitate movement between storage repositories, ensuring compatibility with AAI-based authentication for security. High-speed, reliable transfer mechanisms must be implemented to minimise downtime and enhance workflow automation ([EBTR-181](#)).

Furthermore, researchers require tools to automate recurring data transfers within workflows. The system will provide APIs for scheduling and monitoring transfers, ensuring seamless integration into scientific pipelines. This service will also maintain logs for traceability and support error recovery mechanisms ([EBTR-181](#)).

Metadata Aggregation and Discovery

The Scholarly Metadata Aggregator Service is central to making research outputs more discoverable. It will support harvesting metadata via OAI-PMH and REST APIs, ensuring that service providers can normalise, map and filter metadata across repositories. The

aggregator must comply with FAIR principles²⁰ to enhance metadata accessibility ([EBTR-269](#)).

For researchers and developers willing to explore cross-disciplinary and cross-data source metadata, the EF will offer a search interface. The system will integrate with persistent identifiers (e.g., DOI) and support various export formats (JSON, XML, etc.), ensuring compatibility with different research domains. Scalability is critical to accommodate increasing metadata sources over time ([EBTR-269](#)).

Interactive and Collaborative Data Analysis

To support scientific computing and visualisation, the EOSC Data Analysis Environment will provide researchers with pre-configured interactive tools such as Jupyter Notebooks and RStudio. These tools must be provisioned dynamically in a secure environment, supporting containerised execution for reproducibility ([EBTR-270](#)).

Collaboration is also a priority. Research teams need shared workspaces with access controls, versioning mechanisms for code and results, and the ability to generate citation-ready PIDs for published work. This will allow seamless geographically distributed research collaboration while ensuring security and high availability ([EBTR-270](#)).

Table 3-1. Use cases scenarios and Epics

Requirement	User Story	Technical Implementation	EOSC Components	Epic Reference
Deployable Service Onboarding	A service provider wants to onboard a service and make it deployable for end users.	Providers must be able to register their services in the Resource Catalogue, linking them to Interoperability Guidelines and defining TOSCA-based configuration templates.	EOSC Deployment Service, Service Catalogue	EBTR-270
Service Deployment via Marketplace	An end user needs to deploy an onboarded service dynamically.	The Marketplace must allow users to trigger service deployments, automatically retrieving and	EOSC Deployment Service, Marketplace,	EBTR-270

²⁰ <https://www.nature.com/articles/sdata201618>

Requirement	User Story	Technical Implementation	EOSC Components	Epic Reference
		displaying execution locations once completed.	Service Catalogue	
Composing Multiple Services	A researcher wants to combine multiple services into a data-driven workflow.	The Execution Framework must enable the linking and integration of deployable services, ensuring compliance with Interoperability Guidelines.	EOSC Deployment Service, Marketplace	EBTR-270
Secure and Efficient Data Transfer	A researcher needs to transfer large datasets between repositories.	The Data Transfer Service must provide secure, high-speed transfer capabilities, support AAI-based authentication, and ensure compatibility with multiple data formats.	EOSC Data Transfer Service, EOSC AAI	EBTR-181
Automated Data Movement	A researcher wants to automate data transfers as part of a workflow.	Support for scheduled and API-driven transfers, with monitoring and error recovery features.	EOSC Data Transfer Service	EBTR-181
Aggregating Metadata from Multiple Sources	A service provider needs to collect metadata from different repositories.	The Metadata Aggregator Service must support OAI-PMH and REST APIs, standardise metadata formats, and allow	Scholarly Metadata Aggregator, Service Catalogue, IF Registry	EBTR-269

Requirement	User Story	Technical Implementation	EOSC Components	Epic Reference
		advanced search/filtering.		
Cross-Disciplinary Metadata Discovery	A researcher wants to search and retrieve scholarly metadata across disciplines.	Implementation of federated search capabilities, integration with persistent identifiers (DOIs, PIDs), and metadata export in multiple formats.	Scholarly Metadata Aggregator, Service Catalogue, IF Registry	EBTR-269
Interactive Data Analysis Environment	Researchers need scalable, pre-configured computing environments.	Deployment of Jupyter, RStudio and other solutions , supporting secure data storage and high-performance computing.	EOSC Deployment Service, Service Catalogue, IF Registry, Marketplace	EBTR-270
Collaborative Research and Reproducibility	Research teams need shared workspaces for analysis and result versioning.	Version-controlled workspaces, shared data storage, and DOI/PID-linked outputs for better reproducibility and collaboration.	EOSC Deployment Service, Service Catalogue, IF Registry, Marketplace	EBTR-270

Marketplace

As illustrated in [Figure 3-2](#), deployable services from the Service Catalogue will also be integrated into the Marketplace. This enhancement aligns with the ongoing efforts to improve service deployability and accessibility within the EOSC ecosystem.

Planned Enhancements:

- Marketplace Extensions for EF Framework Integration ([EBTR-20](#)) – The Marketplace will embed the EOSC Execution Framework (EF) capabilities to enable seamless resource deployability. One possible approach involves onboarding deployable services into the Service Catalogue, allowing the Marketplace to retrieve them and automatically generate offers based on referenced TOSCA templates. End users would be able to discover deployable services in a dedicated Marketplace data collection and place orders while specifying dynamic parameters. The Marketplace would then communicate with the Deployment Service (DS) to provision the requested environment on a cloud platform. However, this is just one of many possible solutions, and alternative implementations may be explored based on evolving needs and technical considerations;
- Availability of Key Applications in the EOSC Marketplace ([EBTR-18](#)) – Applications such as Data Transfer Service (through the Deployment Service), Scholarly Metadata Aggregator Service, and Data Analysis Environment will be made available within the Marketplace.

To achieve these objectives, the logical architecture of the Marketplace will be enhanced with the following changes:

The Marketplace will be integrated with the Deployment Service to enable the automated provisioning of environments for end users. Additionally, it will support the submission of data sources required for the requested environment. The Deployment Service will then forward this information to the Data Transfer Service, which will handle the transfer of the requested data to the designated environment.

Figure 3-2. Logical architecture of EOSC Marketplace including new integrations.

IF Registry

The IF Registry Architecture [Figure 2-4](#) was already presented in [Section 2.1.2](#).

The EOSC IF Registry will evolve from being a simple collection of human-readable guidelines (which are instructions that EOSC Providers must implement to enable the desired functionality and interoperability between their EOSC services and/or research products) to a collection of guidelines that support machine-composability of resources. For this, the notion of *Configuration Templates* for Guidelines is introduced: These are structured metadata profiles that allow providers to detail the actual access parameters of their services according to the guidelines ([EBTR-117](#), [EBTR-118](#)). As such, Configuration Templates are defined together with a Guideline; Guideline providers can onboard Guidelines and manage their Configuration Template(s) through the Providers Portal or through an upgrade of the existing API for onboarding and managing Guidelines. The Providers Portal will offer a generic editor for Configuration Templates to allow the abstract definition of the template's schema: i.e. fields, types and sets of allowed values and the general structure of template metadata.

These guidelines may reference various existing standards, protocols and processes, in a manner that allows Providers to understand how to design and configure services to be part

of the EOSC ecosystem. Although the Interoperability Guidelines are helpful to humans, they do not allow for automated deployment or metadata consistency checks.

Based on the above, the EOSC Service Catalogue will be modified to accommodate *Service Configurations* (which are actually Configuration Template Instances for a specific Service related to an IF Guideline); This requires that the Providers Dashboard will be upgraded to support editing of Configuration Template instances for Services linked to Guidelines through a UI; moreover, these instances need to be persisted in the Service Registry and be part of the data that the Service Catalogue shares with other Core Components (particularly the Marketplace) through messaging or through an API ([EBTR-119](#)). Finally, the IF Registry will be upgraded to offer the ability to access associated IF Guidelines and related software libraries of an onboarded service (through an API or through EOSC Messaging) to the Marketplace UIs ([EBTR-120](#)).

Deployment Service

The Deployment Service (DS) aims to provide automated integration and composability of data sources, software tools and computing infrastructures.

The first step is the creation and addition of Guidelines for TOSCA deployable services to the EOSC IF Registry. This guideline describes how to onboard a service in the Service Catalogue with the option to deploy it ([EBTR-129](#)). For such deployable services, a dedicated template needs to be filled out following the TOSCA specification, but a simplified version will be used to enable any user without TOSCA knowledge to define it.

The DS requires the deployment of compute services combined with the staging of datasets inside the deployed virtualised infrastructure. This way, the data will be ready for processing after its dynamic prefetching. So, a key enhancement of the DS is supporting the deployment of datasets close to the compute services.

To that aim, the TOSCA specification is extended to describe the location of the datasets. This requires adding the required node types to describe data sets and the relations with the compute resources ([EBTR-130](#)). However, the DS should also be extended to enable automated data staging capabilities to fetch the data sources from multiple open repositories and make them available to the dynamically provisioned virtual infrastructure ([EBTR-131](#)).

[Figure 3-3](#) presents a general diagram of DS considering the order of execution in the workflow.

Figure 3-3. Deployment Service architecture.

Additionally, the Deployment Service will interact with the Dynamic DNS Service to assign DNS entries during deployment, and automatically request TLS certificates, thus ensuring secure access (e.g., HTTPS) for deployed services without external dependencies such as Let's Encrypt. This automation minimises user intervention and provides secure, ready-to-use infrastructure for data-driven applications (EBTR-132). This task will require extending the current DS functionality to adapt to the new DyDNS²¹ APIs regarding host additions and TLS certificate generation.

3.2. Composability-based Applications

3.2.1. Scholarly Communication Repository Harvester

This use case demonstrates how the EOSC Execution Framework (EF) can be leveraged to develop services utilising a service-oriented approach, allowing for dynamic interoperability with Exchange services by discovering and interacting with their APIs. It addresses a

²¹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Dynamic_DNS

common scenario in scholarly communication where users need to collect bibliographic metadata records from institutional or thematic repositories for data analysis purposes or to build aggregations of multiple repositories. The idea is to create a web application that enables a user, typically a researcher or developer, to select a repository registered in the EOSC service catalogue, harvest its metadata record collections, and store the records at a preferred location. Specifically, to implement such a workflow, the use case involves repositories that provide OAI-PMH APIs (a common protocol in the scholarly communication domain) and FTP endpoints for targeting an internet storage location.

Figure 3-4. Scholarly Communication Repository Harvester: component architecture and interaction with Execution Framework services and external repositories

In order to implement the use case, the following tasks must be accomplished:

Preparation of benchmark data: [EBTR-342](#)

- Ensuring that a curated set of institutional or thematic (or catch-all) repositories are registered to the EOSC Catalogue as Data Sources;
- Ensuring that EOSC IF Guidelines for Data Sources (currently available in the EOSC Catalogue) are associated with a *configuration template* that allows service owners to provide detailed OAI-PMH end points for their repositories as *configuration instances*;
- Ensuring that a curated set of repositories compliant with the EOSC IF Guidelines for Data Sources provides configuration instances for their OAI-PMH end points.

Design and implementation of the application back-end: [EBTR-343](#)

- Querying the EOSC Service Catalogue APIs to search for Data Sources that are compatible with the EOSC IF Guidelines for Data Sources and provide an OAI-PMH end point;
- Invoking a given OAI-PMH end point (with given parameters) to download the records into a local temporary storage;
- Invoking the EOSC Data Transfer APIs with an FTP endpoint (and credentials) to ensure the downloaded data can be transferred to the FTP location.

Design and implementation of the application front-end that, by interacting with the back-end, is capable of: [EBTR-344](#)

- Supporting users at performing searches to find OAI-PMH-compatible repositories in the EOSC Service Catalogue and consulting the result list;
- Supporting users at selecting one repository, provide the necessary OAI-PMH parameters (metadata format of interest, from/to date of the records, OAI-set, number of records), and FTP endpoint (with credentials if necessary).

3.2.2. Data Transfers on deployment

This application demonstrates a scenario where a user needs to deploy datasets onto a specific infrastructure. A common example is training a machine learning (ML) model, which requires high-performance hardware and large datasets. In this case, the user already knows the relevant dataset(s), their location, the required infrastructure, and the software needed for model training and generation.

The Data Transfer service underlying this application requires two inputs: a DOI (or multiple DOIs) identifying the datasets and a destination storage location (address or URL) where the datasets should be transferred. Leveraging CERN's FTS service, the Data Transfer handles dataset parsing, caching, authentication, and movement once the required infrastructure is provisioned via the Deployment Service.

- Requirement: The DS must use automated data staging capabilities ([EBTR-10](#))
 - Integrate EF/DS with DT: Manage data transfer during infrastructure deployment ([EBTR-349](#));
 - Integrate DT in Mp-DS ordering: Marketplace to request dataset information when EF/DS with DT is ordered ([EBTR-350](#));
 - Enhancing S3 Storage Integration in EOSC Data Transfer ([EBTR-351](#)).

[Figure 3-5](#) illustrates the timeline and workflow of the components involved in this process.

Figure 3-5. Data transfer deployment workflow.

3.2.3. Setting up a Data Analysis Environment

Users can find research data, identify the service they may need for its analysis or processing, and deploy both services and data at the same site to enable data analysis.

Workflow: (i) The user finds a product of interest in the Marketplace, which recommends the usage of a deployable service for its processing; (ii) The user can configure (via a UI) an

environment where the data can be processed, and can set its access-point domain; (iii) The dataset are staged into the storage allocated for the application; (iv) The user is returned the access point of the application environment.

Figure 3-6. Data analysis environment set-up workflow.

Figure 3-6 depicts the workflow to set up a data analysis environment, using green to highlight new components or features needed to implement it (EBTR-270) that have been described in detail in Section 3.1. Note that two options will be supported in respect of the logical proximity of a storage system to the computation. If the cloud provider offers a storage system it will be used to store the data sets required by the computation. In this case, the Data Transfer Service will be used to manage the data movement from the Open Data Repository to the cloud provider storage system. Otherwise, the data sets will be directly staged within the provisioned virtualised infrastructure. Leveraging libraries such as DataHugger²², this functionality will be integrated with Ansible Roles²³ and TOSCA²⁴ templates managed by the DS.

²² <https://j535d165.github.io/datahugger/>

²³ https://docs.ansible.com/ansible/latest/playbook_guide/playbooks_reuse_roles.html

²⁴ <https://docs.oasis-open.org/tosca/TOSCA/v2.0/TOSCA-v2.0.html>

4. Conclusion

This document concludes the design activities of the EOSC Beyond Work Package 10, clearly outlining the architecture and implementation roadmap for the EOSC Integration Suite (IS) and Execution Framework (EF). Building upon previously identified gaps and user-driven requirements (as presented in deliverable D10.1), we have detailed the structural components and steps required for practical implementation.

The Integration Suite provides a structured repository of software components, known as Adapters, enabling seamless integration of EOSC services. It simplifies the sharing, discovery, and utilisation of Adapters, significantly enhancing the interoperability of resources within the EOSC community. The Adapters facilitate streamlined integration processes, enabling service providers and researchers to efficiently leverage EOSC resources for diverse use cases.

The Execution Framework complements the Integration Suite by supporting automated and dynamic deployment of services using TOSCA-compliant configurations. This significantly reduces complexity, allowing service providers to offer deployable resources and end users to effortlessly instantiate customised research environments and workflows. It also supports composability, enabling flexible orchestration of multiple services and enhancing the research experience.

The combined deployment of IS and EF ensures a robust and highly adaptable ecosystem that promotes community collaboration and innovation. The detailed architectures, implementation plans, and design components presented in this report lay a solid foundation for the upcoming phases of implementation in Work Packages 11 and 13. Ultimately, the successful realisation of IS and EF will substantially advance the EOSC's mission to support open science through improved accessibility, interoperability, and automation of digital research services across Europe.